

DEGREE OF ADHERENCE TO TREATMENT REGULATIONS OF TEENAGERS INFECTED WITH TUBERCULOSIS

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Abstract: Taking into account the compliance of children and adolescents, it is necessary to take into account the compliance, readiness, and ability of parents to follow the doctor's recommendations. Parents may not understand the severity of the disease and its consequences. In this regard, it is possible not to take medicines on time, to stop treatment arbitrarily, and to be afraid of the side effects of medicines. In treatment, the same attitude is formed in the child. It is especially important to consider these conditions in chronic diseases. An important problem in pediatric practice has become the formation of adherence to treatment not only in children and adolescents but also in their parents. The need to inform the patient and his relatives, understand the information provided, and follow the medical recommendations is an important and necessary condition for the formation of compliance.

Keywords: treatment procedure, adolescent, tuberculosis, competence.

Significance: The relevance of the study is that, despite the success achieved by phthisis doctors in the treatment of tuberculosis, drug-resistant forms have increased in recent years against the background of the decrease of primary forms of tuberculosis, not only in adults but also in children and adolescents. The success of the treatment depends on the level of adherence to the treatment, the main component of which is the compliance of the patient. Compliance can be defined as the degree of agreement, the degree to which a person's behavior is consistent with what the doctor recommends. In some studies, the compliant patient is viewed as passive, and forced to comply with medical interventions. A patient with a high level of compliance is an active participant in the treatment process and accepts medical recommendations and treatment strategies voluntarily and without belief [1,5,37]. In the WHO review "Adherence to long-term therapy: evidence for action" [18,25,33], the main psychologically determined factors of commitment are listed as the behavior of health workers, health care organizations, and psychosocial characteristics of patients [15,22, 28].

In therapeutic, diagnostic, and rehabilitation processes in pediatrics, the family's social status, financial situation, level of culture, national and religious affiliation, awareness in the field of medicine, level of knowledge of parents, attitude to illness and treatment, etc. are important. In dysfunctional families, stress

has long-term effects on the child's personality. An unhealthy psychological environment and disruption of family education cause helplessness and dependency in children and adolescents. This helps to change the structure of the internal picture of their health and diseases [8,19].

When considering the suitability of children and adolescents, the suitability, readiness, and ability of the parents to follow the doctor's recommendations should be taken into account. Parents may not understand the severity of the disease and its consequences. In this regard, it is possible not to take medicines on time, to stop treatment arbitrarily, and to be afraid of the side effects of medicines[24,30,32]. In treatment, the same attitude is formed in the child. It is especially important to consider these conditions in chronic diseases. An important problem in pediatric practice has become the formation of treatment adherence not only in children and adolescents but also in their parents. The need to inform the patient and his relatives, understand the information provided, and follow the medical recommendations is an important and necessary condition for the formation of compliance. In addition, the doctor should take into account the psychological state of family members, their financial situation, and their physical health.

Objective: The objective of the study is to study the level of adherence to the treatment regimen of adolescents with tuberculosis.

Materials and methods: The total number of the experimental group was 160 people aged 13-18 (76 boys and 84 girls), and the average age of the respondents was 15.5 years. The study included adolescents who were treated in the children's department of the Center for Physiology and Pulmonology. Criteria for inclusion in the experimental group: informed consent for participation in the study, tuberculosis of intrathoracic lymph nodes, primary tuberculosis complex, focal tuberculosis, inflamed tuberculosis, and tuberculosis pleurisy. Control group accordingly.

The study of the level of compliance of adolescents was carried out using the questionnaire "Level of compliance". Fisher's angular transformation criterion was used to compare the frequency of occurrence of the indicator we were interested in.

Results and discussion: Overall compliance and its components were studied in a group of adolescents with tuberculosis and in a control group.

The results obtained in the group of adolescents with tuberculosis show that the high level of social compatibility among adolescents aged 13-15 years is much lower (22%) than among adolescents aged 16-18 years (65%). Children of the older adolescent group need support and a reliable relationship with a doctor. They rely on the opinion of medical staff, care about the impression they make on others, and try to follow the doctor's recommendations. In addition, this indicator is evident in young men aged 16-18. Moderate severity of social competence is significantly more common in girls aged 13-15 (60%). At this age, social status has not yet been determined. Patients usually act "according to the situation". Adolescents who are aware of the need for treatment try to avoid side effects caused by the use of drugs, the duration of treatment, and the need for a long stay in the hospital or ambulatory care. Low compliance is significantly more common among boys aged 13-15. They focus only on their feelings and their decisions. They tend to have their own opinion and often engage in confrontations, sometimes openly. Such teenagers cause conflicts with the doctor and other children in the department. They tend to impose their views on other children and parents. Thus, high social conformity is reliably more common ($p < 0.01$) in boys aged 16-18, and low in boys aged 13-15.

In the control group, high indicators of social competence are more common in the group of boys aged 16-18 years (17%). In most cases, the control group's 13-18-year-old teenagers have a low level of social compatibility (53% in the 13-15-year-old group and 52% in the 16-18-year-old group). This shows that teenagers are not inclined to take the recommendations of doctors seriously, they openly protest treatment, they seek to prove their point of view, and their opinion is the only truth. They believe that treatment is

optional and drugs are "poison", they don't want to think about the diseases they may develop and remember their own illnesses. The severity of the emotional component of compliance differs in the subjects of the experimental and control groups, as well as in age subgroups and gender within these groups. Thus, adolescents aged 13-15 years are distinguished by high values of emotional competence (60%), boys (56%) and girls (58%). Adolescents are characterized by sensitivity, the formation of affection, and excessive anxiety about the consequences of illness and treatment. They are ready to cooperate with the doctor and strive to fulfill his appointment. Increased anxiety and frequent mood swings are observed. They try to put the responsibility for their health on the doctor and on the parents. They are good executors of medical instructions. Adolescents aged 16-18 years, on the other hand, underestimate the severity of the disease and are hesitant about the disease and treatment. They can neglect to comply with medical instructions and treatment, reduce its quality, and increase its duration. The average indicator of emotional competence is characteristic of 69% of adolescents aged 16-18 years with tuberculosis. 10% of adolescents aged 13-15 and 17% of adolescents aged 16-18 were found to have a low level of emotional compatibility. They are distinguished by emotional stability, restraint, self-confidence, and caution. There is a tendency to ignore treatment aspects and to underestimate the severity of the disease. In the control group, 13% of adolescents aged 13-15 years and 12% of boys and girls aged 16-18 years had a high level of emotional compatibility. In most cases (43% and 53% in the subgroups aged 13-15 and 16-18, respectively), an average level of emotional compatibility was determined. 45% of 13-15 year olds and 37% of 16-18 year olds have low emotional compatibility. During the study, statistically reliable differences ($p < 0.01$) in the severity of behavioral compliance were found in the experimental and control groups depending on gender and age. A high level of behavior is observed in 9% of adolescents aged 13-15 years (10% and 9% of boys and girls, respectively) and 36% of adolescents aged 16-18 years in the experimental group. Patients of this group strive to strictly adhere to medical recommendations aimed at overcoming the disease, adhere to the treatment regimen, and strive to cooperate with the doctor. Behavior is stable and ready for treatment. Low indicators of behavior were observed in 39% of adolescents aged 13-15 years and 22% of adolescents aged 16-18 years in the experimental group. This is manifested in the tendency to be affected by inconsistency, feelings, and situations, which negatively affect the treatment process and results. Such adolescents believe that the severity of the disease is exaggerated and that everything will pass by itself. Behavior is characterized by irresponsibility and disorder.

In the control group, 10% of adolescents aged 13-15 years have a high level of compliance. 48% of adolescents aged 13-15 years and 32% of adolescents aged 16-18 years were diagnosed with low levels. The general competence level of teenagers was determined. 22% of adolescents aged 13-15 years and 42% of adolescents aged 16-18 years have a high rate. They are distinguished by the desire to enter into a trusting relationship with the doctor, and to rely on his opinion. There is obedience to the doctor who is accepted as a reliable person. Such adolescents contribute to the treatment process, control it, and are very concerned about the possible negative consequences of the disease. Psychologically, teenagers in this group are ready to fight the disease with the help of a doctor. Average compliance rates were 75% of 13-15-year-olds and 56% of 16-18-year-olds diagnosed. Adolescents in this group do not have a defined position on treatment, they act according to the situation. Following the treatment procedure, it is common for respondents to deny the need for it. The position of teenagers depends on motivation. Behavior is characterized by instability. They underestimate the severity of the disease, which leads to disobedience to medical recommendations and treatment regimens. At the same time, subjects are characterized by anxiety and pessimism about the future.

6% of 13-15 year olds and 5% of 16-18 year olds have low compliance. Such subjects are characterized by independence in decision-making, lack of agreement with the doctor on treatment, and a tendency to open confrontation. They are focused only on rational and logical methods of treatment. They often doubt the correctness of medical instructions, and consider them incorrect and useless. The seriousness of the disease

is underestimated, it satisfies their desires and disrupts the treatment regimen.

In the control group, 11% of adolescents aged 13-15 years and 14% of adolescents aged 16-18 years had a high level of general competence. On average, 42% of adolescents aged 13-15 and 48% of adolescents aged 16-18 were observed. A low level of overall compliance is observed in 48% of adolescents aged 13-15 and 41% of adolescents aged 16-18.

The level of social, emotional, behavioral, and general adjustment was compared in adolescents with tuberculosis according to gender and age. Within the age subgroups, it was found that there were no statistically significant differences in compliance severity in boys and girls with tuberculosis. At the same time, the severity of compliance components - social, emotional, and behavioral - differ in age subgroups of adolescents in the experimental group. Thus, 19% of adolescents aged 13-15 years have a high level of social conformity, but 60% of subjects aged 16-18 years; a high level of emotional compatibility was diagnosed in 57% of adolescents aged 13-15 and 17% of boys and girls aged 16-18; only 9% of adolescents aged 13-15 years have high indicators of behavioral compatibility, this indicator is 36% in the subgroup of 16-18 years.

Conclusion: Thus, adolescents with tuberculosis are distinguished by high social compatibility in the subgroup of 16-18 years and low in 13-15 years. At the same time, high values of emotional compatibility are noted in 13-15-year-olds, and the predominance of average values in the subgroup of 16-18-year-olds. Most of the studied adolescents have average indicators of behavioral compatibility, regardless of gender and age. Overall compliance is high with 22% of 13-15 year olds and 42% of 16-18 year olds. Low rates of compliance were diagnosed in only 6% and 5% of adolescents aged 13-15 and 16-18, respectively. This shows that the opinion on the treatment of adolescents in this group is not determined, they act according to the situation; and try to comply with treatment but deny the need for it. The success of treatment and interaction with the doctor depends on motivation. Behavior is unstable. The severity of the disease is underestimated, which leads to violations of the rules of compliance with medical recommendations and treatment regimens. Patients are concerned about the future but in a pessimistic mood.

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